

CRITERIAS FOR IMPROVING THE CIVIC POSITION IN THE TEACHING OF SPECIALIZED SCIENCES

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Abstract: Today, in the development of the new Uzbekistan, on the basis of the strategic reforms implemented in the education system, the issue of forming an active citizenship position among young people is one of the urgent tasks. This article examines the role of innovative pedagogical technologies in the teaching of social-humanitarian and specialized sciences, and analyzes its unique innovative methods.

Key words: civic position, value, thinking, criterias for civic position, innovative development, strategy, aesthetic culture.

Today, many studies have been conducted by philosophers and pedagogues on improving the citizenship position of students by teaching socio-humanitarian and specialized subjects on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies. In these studies, it is justified that the social and historical development of the individual society has been achieved due to the fact that the position of citizenship is a society where national values are established, the rule of law is ensured, humane and just. In particular, the promoters of the theoretical idea of innovative technologies are B. Bloom, J. Blok, D. Kratvol, V. P. Bespalko, V. M. Klarin, B. T. Likhachyov, J. Carroll, Yu. Kulyutkin, V. A. Selastyonin, M. Chashanov, B. A. Farberman, N. Sayidakhmedov, M. Ochilov, K. Zaripov, O'. Tolipov, J. Yoldoshev, M. Usmonboyeva, N. Avliyokulov, M. Kh. Makhmudov, O. Rozikov, B. Adizov, S. Ogayev, I. Lerner, B.Khojayev, Sh.Olimov, S.Usmonov and others in their research studies have shown that innovative technologies are based on the principles of personal development and personal development and the activation of students, their educational activities and the level of education who have proved that they serve for promotion.

Citizenship position is the eternal dream, desire and rare discovery of mankind. In this, the rule of law among the members of the society, free and independent living, social justice is established, and the management system is oriented towards the interests of people.

In researching the topic of this article, the 60310700 - Political science education course was taken as an example to clarify the issue of improving the

citizenship position of students by teaching social-humanitarian and specialized subjects on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies. These issues in the content of socio-humanitarian and specialized sciences made it possible to practically solve the following tasks facing the research and future political scientists:

1. In the process of socio-economic development and spiritual-political life of a person, information was formed that these information should occupy a leading place.

2. The importance of this knowledge in the development of the country, the well-being of the people, the peace of the country, and the development of production was brought to their minds.

3. To learn that information in the content of sciences is of primary importance in the formation and development of socio-political, spiritual-economic, moral-legal views, beliefs of any specialist.

4. Believing that social and humanitarian sciences have an important position for the development of world civilization, international harmony, and international solidarity.

5. The concept of serving as an important resource for the development of creativity, creativity, creativity skills was formed along with the improvement of independent thinking in future highly educated specialists.

Taking into account these issues, the following criteria for improving the citizenship position of future political scientists by studying social-humanitarian and specialized sciences were determined in the research process:

1. To respect the laws of national development, state symbols (constitution, flag, anthem, seal, currency), to realize that their preservation is a civic duty and responsibility, to have a sense of patriotism.

2. Containing the need to show initiative, creativity, creativity and work in the way of building a new Uzbekistan, peace of the country, freedom and development of the Motherland, and people's well-being;

3. To understand the content of great thinkers, representatives of science, rich and huge spiritual heritage, national and universal values, and to have the feeling of preserving and honoring them.

4. To understand the essence of such concepts as the perfect person, citizenship, active citizenship, civic position, civic duty, responsibility, faith, and to cultivate these qualities in oneself.

5. Having a sense of internationalism (culture of inter-national communication), inter-religious tolerance (tolerance), showing respect for the culture and traditions of other nations and peoples.

6. Adhering to a healthy lifestyle, awareness, legal and ethical norms, striving to build one's life and activity, a healthy lifestyle, based on the laws of the culture of awareness.

It should be recognized that innovative technologies, based on humanitarian and democratic principles, can activate students, speed up the training process, effectively organize and manage the educational activities of learners, and improve the effectiveness of conveying educational information to the minds of young learners. It is a didactic process that provides axiological, acmeological, technological, activity-organizational, task-oriented approach in the organization of teaching activities [3].

Taking into account the fact that the development of the civic position of future political scientists will be used in the objects of our research, to apply the pedagogical innovation (forms, methods, methods, tools of education) specified in the model to the process of theoretical and practical training, and activities based on this system was designed. These aspects were supplemented by the use of non-traditional forms of teaching, interactive methods and computer technology included in the content of the didactic-technological system. The effectiveness of this system was confirmed by the experimental work carried out in our research. Now let's consider the innovative-technological aspect:

1. Methodological aspect. This aspect is based on fundamental ideas in the content of sciences, ideas about civil society and perfect human being and medical science of the past scholars, Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Civil Code, religious teachings, national and universal values, New It covers information that illuminates the ideology of Uzbekistan.

2. Psychological aspect. This aspect involves the mental preparation of future political scientists to understand the concepts of civil culture in the content of the taught subjects, the organization of educational work in the teacher-student relationship, in which the content of the training is based on the interest, needs, and interests of the learner-student. It will consist of organization based on educational motives and professional orientation.

3. Activity-content aspect. This aspect means that it is necessary to establish the relationship between the concepts of civil culture in the content of subjects and the expression of specific events, topics, departments, and

disciplines, and to consider the practical application of teacher-student cooperation activities in the study of concepts.

4. Organizational-methodical aspect. In applying this aspect, the teacher shows the need to develop a program for mastering the main ideas in the content of the sciences, concepts of civil culture related to them and their essence, content, functions, and a specific form and method of its practical application. , refers to creating, selecting and applying methods and tools.

5. Practical aspect. This aspect implies the application of concepts of civil culture to professional activity and personal life based on learned and mastered knowledge, skills, and abilities.

Regional-specific aspect. This aspect is the effective use of effective ways of educating students and young people by comparing the concepts of civil culture expressed in the content of socio-humanitarian and specialized sciences and the main fundamental sources with the content of customs, traditions, national values, ceremonies of the region and the destination. covered issues such as

In short, by teaching socio-humanitarian and specialized subjects on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies, determining the possibilities of these subjects in the development of civil culture in students and taking into account the interests of students, independent creative thinking from the point of view of the problem, and teaching them to conduct cultural communication brought positive results. It includes non-traditional classes such as business games, competition classes, intellectual ring, theatrical classes, group work, creative contests, auction classes, bait-baraks, debate classes, excursion classes, field of miracles. is of great pedagogical importance.

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